

METACOGNITIVE LEARNING IN SOLVING MATHEMATICAL WORD PROBLEMS

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Metacognitive Learning in Solving Mathematical Word Problems

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Abstract

The metacognition in mathematics learning on solving word problems, explicitly described the solving strategies using metacognition anchored from the two metacognitive components. The students' knowledge of cognition in mathematics learning in terms of declarative knowledge utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information techniques which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts such as reading and recalling, translating, identifying mathematical concepts, determining the needed information, and understanding the leading question. Students' procedural knowledge in mathematics learning utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as substituting, representing, and organizing process, which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to the substitution process, use of representation while solving, and organizing solution coherently and logically. Substituting, representing, and organizing process is the execution of plan, strategy, model, idea, decision, or method and the realization of an application of the subject. Students' conditional knowledge in mathematics learning utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as questioning the problem and their own practices, which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to question the problem, consistent practice to develop familiarity, solution appropriateness, exploring possible solutions, and thinking of ways to approach the problem. Students' regulation of cognition in mathematics learning in terms of planning utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as breaking down, illustrating, and labelling and thinking about the information, formula, and steps which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to write down the information in the problem, determine the required formula, think about the steps before solving, breakdown the problem, draw illustration, and put labelling. Students' monitoring regulation in mathematics learning utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as making sense of their own work and verifying solutions, which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to second thoughts during and after solving, recognizing errors in the solution, familiarity towards the problem, checking of works step by step, reflecting from time to time, and use of scratch to draft solutions. Students' evaluating regulation in mathematics learning utilized specific metacognitive strategies such as reviewing and revising which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to review calculations and procedures, use strategies to check answers, draw conclusions, think of alternative ways after completing a task, and revising solutions if not correct.

Keywords: *metacognition, metacognitive learning, mathematical word problems*

Introduction

There are findings that highlight that learners with high metacognition perform better in math (including problem solving) than learners with weak metacognition (Jaafar & Ayub, 2010; Özsoy, 2010). In addition, some studies indicate that metacognition is significant predictor of achievement in mathematics (Deseote & Roeyers, 2006; Stillman & Mevarech, 2010; Van der Stel et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2011).

The studies of Baker (1989), Cross and Pans (1998), Garner (1987), Garner (1990), King (1991), Lorch et al. (1993), Pintrich et al. (2000), Pressley et al. (1987), Schneider and Presly (1989), and Veenman et al. (2006) focused on the importance of knowledge of cognition. While studies of Bereiter and Scardamalia (1987), Delclos and Harrington (1991), and Garner and Alexander (1989) focused on regulation of cognition.

Knowledge of cognition is the first component of metacognition which composed of three types namely – declarative, procedural, and conditional. Declarative knowledge pertains to one's awareness of what influences cognitions and includes person and task that can be strategy variables. (Veenman et al., 2006) Procedural knowledge pertains is a large variety of strategies or skills (Pintrich et al., 2000; Pressley et al., 1987; Veenman et al., 2006) for how skill operate or how can be applied. According to Cross and Paris (1988), conditional knowledge pertains to one's knowing when and why to use declarative and procedural knowledge (Garner, 1990).

In terms of declarative knowledge of cognition, sample research investigating metamemory is an example of declarative processes that indicates that adults are more knowledgeable than children about cognitive processes associated with memory (Baker, 1989). Comparatively, good learners are more knowledgeable about their own memory than those poor learners (Garner, 1987; Schneider & Pressley, 1989).

With regards to procedural knowledge of cognition, King (1991) reveals that helping younger learners increase one's procedural knowledge to improve their solving performance. One example is when he compared groups of fifth-grade students in which each of them solved problems using a problem-solving prompt card or solved problems even without it. The explicit training group who received procedural training on how to use the prompt card solved more problems on paper-and-pencil tests and performed better on a

novel computer task than the control group.

As to conditional knowledge of cognition, a sample of college learners were renowned among the processing demands of ten different types of situations while reading (Lorch et al., 1993). To better regulate their learning, they selected the most appropriate one from different strategies for each situation. Across the ten situations, the beliefs of students about the relative severity of demands placed on their cognitive resources differed. Recent studies proposed that conditional knowledge development is continuous until at least through middle childhood.

On the other hand, regulation of cognition is the second component of metacognition which is composed of three types namely – planning, monitoring, and evaluating. Bereiter and Scardamalia (1987) presented an in-depth analysis of how good and poor writers draft their writing. A finding stated that the ability to plan and the knowledge about the process of planning develops throughout childhood and adolescence period, which improves histrionically between the ages from 10 to 14. Meanwhile, more experienced writers deal with the engagement in more global that contradicts the local planning but in addition, they are better in terms of planning effectively regardless of text content whereas poor writers are incompetent to do so. These findings are a common sequence of development found when studying other types of regulatory metacognition (Baker, 1989; Garner & Alexander, 1989).

Studies suggest that training and practice improves one's monitoring ability. In the study of Delclos and Harrington (1991) about the ability of a fifth and sixth- grader in solving computer problems after assigning to one out of three conditions: the first group accepted particular problem-solving training; the second group received problem-solving and self-monitoring training, while the last group didn't receive any training. The monitored problem- solving group solved more of the harder and complex problems faster than the remaining groups or control group.

In terms of evaluation of regulation of cognition, studies insinuate that planning skills on knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition are affiliated to evaluation (Baker, 1989). Typical studies include the revisions found by Bereiter and Scardamalia (1987) wherein good writers are better compared to poor writers who were less capable in adopting reader's perspective and had more difficulty in terms of diagnosing text problems and its corrections. This contradistinction was presumed to be the use of different mental models of writing.

Certainly, Garofalo and Lester (1985) stressed the importance of metacognition for mathematical performance analysis and understanding. Referring to the distinction between knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition, they argued that in mathematical performance, not only regulatory metacognitive behaviors but also knowledge of cognition categories of person, task, and strategy are important (Schoenfeld, 1983). Though the latter variables were originally designed to identify metacognitive memory awareness, in the sense of metacognitive effects on mathematical achievement they also seemed relevant.

Conclusively, developing metacognition is the most important construct in this study. The way teachers organize the classroom instruction depends on their knowledge about teaching mathematics. The knowledge is needed for recognizing then applying the teaching opportunities that come up without prior notice. Teachers can depict mathematics as a logical and connected system if they understand bigger ideas with it. As well as they can make multiple students' viewpoints and make it more reasonable. Teachers can only assist students to develop their mathematical ground understanding with substantial content knowledge and the teachers' knowledge on how to develop metacognition among learners will be considered (Hill et al., 2005).

Research Questions

This qualitative study aimed to propose a model of metacognitive learning in solving mathematical word problems. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following statements in pursuit of academic contributions in the area of mathematics education:

1. Describe how learners learn from the instruction and assessment of teachers in terms of the following components of metacognition:
 - 1.1. Knowledge of cognition; and
 - 1.2. Regulation of cognition
2. Propose a model of learning strategies in solving mathematical word problems

Methodology

Research Design

The focus of this study was to develop and propose a model of learning metacognition in solving mathematical word problems which was accomplished through the use of Multiple Case Study Method. Multiple case study was employed to generate concepts from data and identify relationships and patterns between the context and process that may stand as bases for the development of the model for metacognitive learning strategies in solving mathematical word problems.

Participants

The focus of this study was to develop and propose a model of learning metacognition in solving mathematical word problems which was accomplished through the use of Multiple Case Study Method. Multiple case study was employed to generate concepts from data

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Table 1. Overview of the Background Information of the Observed Classes

Participant	No. of Learners			No. of Observed Hours	Topics
	M	F	Total		
T1	10	14	24	4	Distance and Midpoint Formula
T2	12	18	30	4	Distance Between Two Points and Midpoint Formula
T3	14	17	31	4	Central Angles, Inscribed Angles, Tangent, Secant, and Segments
T4	9	16	25	6	Introduction to Circle, Central Angles, and Inscribed Angles
T5	12	14	26	4	Distance between Two Points and Midpoint Formula
T6	14	12	26	6	Introduction to Circle, Central Angles, and Inscribed Angles
T7	11	14	25	4	Central Angles, Inscribed Angles, Tangent, Secant, and Segments, Distance between Two Points
T8	12	17	29	6	Distance between Two Points and Midpoint Formula
T9	12	16	28	4	Introduction to Circle, Central Angles, and Inscribed Angles
T10	14	19	33	4	Distance Formula, Center and Radius of a Circle
T11	15	14	29	6	Midpoint and Distance in the Coordinate Plane
T12	10	12	22	6	Central Angles, Inscribed Angles, Tangent, Secant, and Segments, Distance between Two Points

The number of students in each online session was only few since not all learners could afford to have online classes. These students were given options to choose between modular and online modality. All the students who were in favor of online modality were put into one section and those who chose modular modality were put into another section/s. The number of hours ranged from 4 to 6 which lasted for about 2 to 3 weeks depending on the saturation of the needed data for the study. The coverage of all the topics taught by the teacher-participants as shown in table 1 above were about a circle which was taught during the second grading period. The length of the second grading period in the new normal starts in January and ends in March. Data collection started last November and December during the distribution of the initial survey questionnaire and consent form for the selected participants.

The following are the lists of the learning competencies used during the online observations: (1) derive inductively the solutions among chords, arcs, central angles, and inscribed angles, (2) prove theorems related to chords, arcs, central angles, and inscribed angles, (3) illustrate secant, tangent, segments, and sectors of the circle, (4) prove theorems on sectors, tangents, and segments, (5) solve problems on circles, (6) derive the distance formula, (7) apply the distance formula to prove some geometric properties, (8) solve problems using midpoint formula, (9) illustrate the center and radius of the equation of the circle, and (10) determine the center and radius of a circle given its equation and vice versa.

The participants of this study were coded according to numbers. However, each participant was encouraged to choose a name or alias to address them during the interview to avoid using their real name for the purpose of anonymity.

Instruments

Data gathering method that was employed in this study was the observation method where the study made use of a video recorder to get the verbatim discussions and facial expressions of the students. The virtual classroom observation guide was divided into three parts and was accomplished by the researcher as an observer.

The research instrument that was used in the study is the online interview guide for selected learners. This was used to interview the selected learners after episodes of classroom observations to determine if they really learned from the instruction and assessment method of their teacher. This questionnaire was divided into two parts and was translated into vernacular language. The first part included descriptions on how learners learn from the instruction and assessment of their teacher in terms of knowledge of cognition and the second was about descriptions on how learners learn from the instruction and assessment of their teacher in terms of regulation of cognition. The researcher gave the learner-participant one example problem about the topic of his/her teacher during online classroom discussion and asked the following questions:

Part 1: Descriptions on how learners learn from the instruction and assessment of their teacher in terms of knowledge of cognition.

[Dictate the Problem] Tell me your understanding about the problem. (Declarative)

[Ask him to solve the problem using talk aloud protocol] Tell me your steps or procedures used to come up with your solution and answer. (Procedural)

How did you know that the solution or technique you used was appropriate to the given word problem? (Conditional)

Part 2: Descriptions on how learners learn from the instruction and assessment of their teacher in terms of regulation of cognition.

How did you plan and organize your activity before solving the problem? (Planning)

Upon solving the problem, did you check whether you are doing the right process or not? Why or why not? (Monitoring)

Tell me how you checked if your answer is correct. (Evaluating)

Finally, the journal writing was used to record all the realization of the researcher after the interviews and observations and to clarify ideas about the research. The basic guidelines and questions for the journal reflections included the descriptions of the setting during the day of the interview, on observation day, and personal thoughts. Descriptions of the situations and the experiences, and reflections on the experiences and discussion were made.

Procedure

Before proceeding to the research process, the conduct of this study went through some protocols and experienced the agony of uncertainty on whether the request was granted or not. The first step began with the letter of permission that was submitted to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent at the Division of Pampanga expressing the intention to conduct a study.

Four qualified learners of each teacher-participant during the episodes of online classroom discussions were identified through the selection criteria provided in this research and they underwent separate online video interviews. After the selection, the researcher requested each teacher-participant to provide the contact number or email address of each selected student. When available, a parent's consent form and assent form were sent to the selected learner-participants. The parent's consent form was a letter of permission to the parent/guardian of the learners before the learners underwent the interview process. An assent form was sent to confirm the willingness of the learner to participate in the online video interview. All scanned/pictured forms with the participant's signature (e.g. letter of invitation, consent form, parent's consent form, and assent form) were requested to be sent immediately via email to schedule the interview proper.

Each learner-participant were requested and given sufficient time to answer each interview question, and they were allowed to respond in their preferred language to be able to expound their thoughts well and provide further examples or sufficient evidence, which took about 15 to 25 minutes for the learner-participant. Moreover, the structure of the interview guide was inspired by the narrative research approach. Therefore, they had the opportunity to reply within the context of their own experience and interpretation.

Each meeting was recorded and any noticeable facial expressions, non-verbal communications, and emotions were documented in the research field notes. Notes and all the data from the recordings and sessions were transcribed immediately after the interview following the purpose of the study and field notes served as inferences for subsequent interview sessions. This was not only beneficial from the aspect of remembering details of each session, but immediate transcriptions served as a measure to help shape future sessions. Reading the complete transcriptions while watching the video allowed the researcher to correct and complete any gap in the transcriptions.

Furthermore, the bracketed forms of the researcher's personal opinions that was brought out during the interview and observation process were taken into consideration. This led to check as well as to compare and contrast the accuracy and consistency during the virtual classroom observations and follow-up interviews. All bracketed notes were included in the interview and observation journal and were processed immediately to ensure that all the data were captured correctly within ethical boundaries.

The basic guidelines and questions for the journal reflections included the descriptions of the setting during the day of the interview and observation, descriptions of the situations and the experiences, and reflections on the experiences and discussion made. In all phases of inquiry, this research tried to involve language instructor and subject instructor to enhance the validity of the study as their varied ideas and views were useful and constructive. The method of internal validity helped the researcher to strengthen the research findings and interpretations.

Every researcher has his own particular beliefs, values, and world views. In general, bracketing the researcher's own beliefs was important to guarantee objectivity with regards to any topic that may affect data collection or analysis. As such, this study was conducted with utmost objectivity and transparency in adhering to the ethical principles and rules, in performing an accurate evaluation as possible, and in honestly reporting the findings throughout the research process.

Data Analysis

The starting point in making interpretation during the data collection and process were memos written as bracketed notes from the results of the online classroom observations and interviews. In preparing systematic interpretation, memos that were relevant to the study were highlighted in the form of observation protocols and were transferred into a computer program as these were taken in a spontaneous manner during the online follow-up interviews or shortly thereafter such as the research journal entries.

Transcripts of video clips from the participants' online interviews and classroom observations were the main source for the analysis. In order to put the pieces of data together in a meaningful relation towards one another, transcripts were read several times to make sense of the whole. That means, transcriptions were read and reread with each subsequent interview, and as such, individual interviews were seen as pieces.

To organize the coding of data, this study utilized the computer software program Microsoft Excel. The open coding was based on deductive and theoretical analysis while axial and selective coding came from a more inductive perspective as the data dictate.

Moreover, a constant comparative method was applied for the data analysis. Codes emerged throughout the comparison of data from the answers of all the research’s participants during the online interviews and classroom observations to seek patterns and consistency in their answers. To explore the objective of this study, comparison of the themes across teachers’ and learners’ responses and researcher’s classroom observations were performed.

Hence, this study adopted and followed the three-phase procedures for grounded theory analysis pertaining to the research’s objectives. The detailed description of the phases were as follows: (1) transcribed teachers’ and learners’ responses from each online interview and observation notes for analysis, (2) analyzed transcripts of observations and interviews to determine initial codes, and (3) created axial codes and selective codes to determine themes and used contrast comparison to develop patterns between the similarities and differences that exist in the teachers’ conceptual understanding and actual classroom practices in conducting instruction and assessment of metacognition in mathematics. Following the three-phase process, the researcher triangulated all data sources to check how the field notes, observation transcripts, and interview transcripts supported the themes found.

Ethical Considerations

To protect their basic rights, privacy, and confidentiality, all direct identifiers were removed. Codes were substituted for identifiers. Data were filed in separate secure locations to protect all participants against indirect identification. No other parties had access to the data collected other than the researcher, participants (for member checking), and the dissertation committee members.

Confidentiality was maintained throughout the transcription procedures by writing pseudonyms for the participants (e.g., S1.1, S1.2, ..., S1.4) and for their schools (e.g., School 1, School 2, ..., School 12) to minimize the risk of the disclosure of personal information and to prevent any link to any part of the data for the protection of the participants and the research’s locale. Following ethical standards in conducting research, the participants were assured that the results and findings of the study were echoed to them.

To ensure the confidentiality of the study, a parent's consent form and assent form were presented for the learner-participants. The online interviews and observations were scheduled at the time that was convenient to them. They were informed that their participation in the study was voluntary. The study also guaranteed that there was no risk involved and they have the right to withdraw anytime without any repercussion. They could also skip any question that they find uncomfortable to answer during the interview. In this study, audio and video recordings were utilized to collect the data on their responses during individual online interviews and classroom observations.

For the learners, this study ensured that their answers and how they responded or acted during the interview were not revealed even if their parents or teachers asked it. Before the online interviews and observations, it was reiterated thoroughly that the purpose of the study to each participant was to ensure that all of them understood the expectation and procedures of the study. At the end of the interview, the participants received a token of appreciation for their effort in answering the interview questions and time spent for the study.

Results and Discussion

Metacognitive Learning from the Teachers’ Instruction and Assessment

From the group of learners, metacognitive techniques used in solving word problems were categorized. Table 2 shows the metacognitive strategies of teachers used by learners. The themes presented in the table summed up the learners’ metacognitive strategies in solving word problems using the two metacognitive components as framework of analysis namely: knowledge of cognition (declarative, procedural, conditional) and regulation of cognition (planning, monitoring, and evaluating).

From these two components of metacognition, several metacognitive strategies were identified from the data. Along with knowledge of cognition, declarative knowledge presents activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information which typifies reading and recalling, translating of concepts, understanding the leading question, identifying mathematical concepts, and determining the needed information.

Table 2. Metacognitive Strategies of Teachers Used by the Students

Metacognitive Components	Types of Metacognition	Metacognitive Strategies	Elaboration of Metacognitive Strategies
Knowledge of Cognition	Declarative Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activating Concepts on the Problem Identifying and Determining Concepts and Information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reading and Recalling Translating of Concepts Understanding the Lead Question Identifying Math Concepts Determining the Needed Information
	Procedural Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substituting, Representing, and Organizing Solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using Substitution while Solving

Regulation of Cognition	Conditional Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questioning the Problem and Own Practices • Generating Solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using Representation while Solving • Organizing Solutions Coherently and Logically • Questioning the Problem • Consistent Practices to Develop Familiarity • Identifying Appropriate Solution • Exploring Alternative Solutions
	Planning Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breaking Down, Illustrating, and Labelling • Thinking about the Information, Formula, and Steps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breaking Down the Problem • Illustrating and Labelling Concepts • Writing Down of Information • Determining Required Formula • Thinking about Steps • Providing Second Thoughts • Recognizing Errors • Familiarity on the Problem • Checking work step by step • Reflecting from time to time • Using scratch to draft solution • Reviewing Calculations and Procedures
	Monitoring Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making Sense on Owns Work • Verifying Solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thinking about Steps • Providing Second Thoughts • Recognizing Errors • Familiarity on the Problem • Checking work step by step • Reflecting from time to time • Using scratch to draft solution • Reviewing Calculations and Procedures
	Evaluating Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing the Process • Revising and Drawing Conclusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using Strategies to Check Answers • Thinking alternative ways after completing the task • Revising the Solution if Not Correct • Drawing Conclusion

Procedural knowledge revealed substituting, representing, and organizing solutions as learners’ metacognitive strategies through substitution and representation while solving and organizing solutions coherently and logically while questioning the problem and own practices and generating solutions from conditional knowledge through questioning the problem, consistent practices to develop familiarity, identifying solution appropriateness, and exploring possible solutions. As to regulation of cognition, learners demonstrated breaking down, illustrating, labelling, and thinking about the information and steps by breaking down the problem, illustrating and labelling concepts, writing down information, determining required formula, and thinking about steps as planning regulation.

Moreover, monitoring regulation displays making sense on own work and verifying solutions from providing a second thoughts, recognizing errors, familiarity of the problem, checking and reflection on work from time to time, and using scratch to draft solution. Finally, reviewing the process and revising and drawing conclusions as strategy for evaluating regulation revealed from reviewing calculations and procedures, using strategies to check answers, thinking alternative ways after completing a task, revising the solution if not correct, and drawing conclusions.

As shown in the table, students’ ways to solve word problems reflect on the amount of strategies used by the teacher in the teaching and assessment process (Borko & Livingston, 1989; Horn & Jang, 2017). Aside from that, more strategies in solving word problems were used in declarative and planning cognition but less in procedural and monitoring to mark the overview of codes generated that would be intensively discussed in the succeeding pages.

1. Learners’ Knowledge of Cognition

Learners’ Knowledge of cognition using its three metacognitive factors (declarative, procedural, and conditional) emerged through a specific metacognitive strategy such as activating concepts on the problem, identifying and determining concepts and information, substituting, representing, and organizing solutions, questioning the problem and own practices, and generating solutions.

1.1. Learners’ Declarative Knowledge

From the data on declarative knowledge, activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers used by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated

by specific metacognitive strategies such as reading and recalling, translating of concepts, understanding the lead question, identifying math concepts, and determining the needed information.

1.1.1. Activating Concepts on Problem

Activating concepts on the problem was one among the elaborated metacognitive strategies used by the students in solving given word problems. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as reading and recalling the lesson intended for the topic, translating the problem based on the level of their understanding, and understanding the leading question given in the problem.

1.1.1.1. Reading and Recalling

Activating concepts through reading the problem carefully and recalling previously learned concepts help learners to understand the task before they answer and to think if they had worked before with a similar problem, S1.1, as one among the students of T1, affirmed that the word problem dictated by the researcher during the online interview session was about distance between the two points. He said that he could understand the word problem by recalling his past lesson which helped him to remember a similar solution to the problem.

I will understand the sample problem by recalling the past topic or lesson that can help me remember a similar solution to this problem. (S1.1)

Similar to S1.1, S1.2, S1.3, and S1.4 were able to recall the lesson of the given problem after reading it. S1.4 revealed during the online interview that he read the given word problem twice before he was able to digest its meaning.

I read the problem twice since it didn't really sink in the first time I did. (S1.4)

Furthermore, aside from reading the problem twice before she understood its meaning, S2.2 used the technique of highlighting the given items or concepts to recall the topic of the problem as she mentioned in her interview.

I read the problem twice to understand it, sir, and I underlined the terms. (S2.2)

In addition, S3.1, S3.2, S3.3, and S3.4 of T3 were able to recall the given word problem about their previously learned topics which were central angles, inscribed angles, and their intercepted arcs. S3.1 stipulated during her interview that the given problem was about finding the measurement of the missing angles given the equation of the intercepted arc and central angle of a circle.

Similarly, S4.1, S4.2, and S4.3 of T4 also recalled that the given word problem was all about the central and inscribed angles including their intercepted arc. According to S4.3, to be able to understand the word problem, he read it thrice. At the same time, S4.1 said that this topic was relevant to angles in a circle because according to her, it clearly portrayed the different angles which were the central, intercepted, and inscribed. On the other hand, all the four students of T5 were able to recall the lesson on the given word problem during their interviews. S5.3 said that he would read and reread the given problem until such time that he would be able to understand it.

Apparently, aside from recalling the topic of the given word problem during their interview sessions, students of T6 who were S6.1, S6.2, and S6.3 used rereading technique to grasp the point of the problem since it was taught to them a week ago but the familiarity of the lesson remained in their system since T6 used parallel problems during their online discussion which, according to S6.2, gave them the chance to remember the topic.

In relation to this, S6.4 of T6 and S7.1 and S7.2 of T7 were able to recall the topic of the given word problem. S6.4 mentioned in his interview that when he saw the circle L in the problem [particularly, the symbol for circle], he was able to identify the lesson but made it more specific when he was trying to analyze the given angle GLK and arc KJ, as he mentioned that this word problem was all about central angle and intercepted arc.

Furthermore, S8.1, S8.2, S8.3, and S8.4 recalled the topic from the given problem by mentioning the use of Cartesian plane. S8.3 said that he was able to recall the lesson because it seemed so familiar to him. Meanwhile, S8.4 asserted that when she graphed the points on the Cartesian plane, they formed horizontal, vertical, and slant line, which helped her to recall the topic. The same was true with the students of T9 who were S9.1, S9.2, and S9.4 that the problem given was similar to the examples of their teacher about central angle and inscribed angle and the intercepted arcs although S9.4 was uncertain regarding the topic.

This is about intercepted arc and circle since these are similar to the examples given by our teacher before in our online class. (S9.4)

Finally, S10.1, S10.3, S11.2, S11.3, and S12.1 were able to distinguish the topic of the given word problem. S12.1 revealed that he read the problem well to understand it and added that he still remembered how to solve the problem.

1.1.1.2. Translating of Concepts

Translating of concepts pertains on how the students translated the problem based on their remembering and understanding about their lessons from their previous discussion. Some students were able to mention during the virtual interview sessions the process of putting the problem into their own words to perceive it. This process requires factual knowledge to be able to translate such problems. S1.4, a

student of T1, mentioned that the problem given to him was all about the distance between two points and added that the task talks about the process of finding the length of the diameter of a circle where point A and point B were given. The same was true with S2.2 who was able to understand the leading question of the problem pertaining to the distances of the houses of the four grade 10 students.

If you look at the problem, it refers to the distance between two points. Let me read it. According to it, along the Jose Balagtas highway are the houses of four grade 10 students namely Jose (8,2), Emilio (1,2), Gabriela (1,9), and Antonio (8,9). So, this pertains to finding the distance between the houses of the four grade 10 students given the four points. (S2.2)

Similarly, S3.3 and S5.2 revealed that their technique to understand the process was through identifying the given, getting an idea from it, and being able to translate it. On the other hand, S6.2 and S7.3, who happened to have the same problem, shared common understandings. According to S7.3, the given problem was all about the circle L which happened to have $x + 128$ and $x + 48$ as the given equations, the task of which was to find the value of x to be able to determine the measurement of angle GLK, angle KLJ, and arc KG.

Finally, S10.4 and S12.1 mentioned that the problem about the circle given to them during the interview had no structured formula, hence the solution and the equation would depend on how one would analyze the problem.

1.1.1.3. Understanding the Lead Question

Understanding the leading question of the problem was the last part of the activating concepts of the problem, which required factual knowledge to be able to comprehend what the problem was about. S3.3 said that the leading question of the problem given to her was to identify the measures of the central angle and its intercepted arc. This portion meant understanding the leading question. As S3.4 mentioned, it was very important to comprehend what the lead question required him to find out before being able to solve a particular problem. S3.4 added that he tried to find the length of the diameter of a circle given its two points along the circumference.

Moreover, S5.3 said that he read the question carefully before heading to the process of solving the problem. Similar to S5.3, S5.2 stated that understanding the question would help him prevent mistakes. The same was true with S5.4 who expounded that understanding the problem helped him get a better idea on how to start his solution.

S6.2, S6.3, and S6.4 students of T6 mentioned that they read and understand the leading question carefully before starting to do their own process. S6.2 added that at first he was estimating how he would approach the problem at first.

I try to understand carefully/well first, sir, before I proceed with solving the problem. (S6.2)

In addition, S8.1 and S8.3 highlighted the given in the problem as their technique to understand the lead question. Furthermore, S9.2 and S12.4 both did not understand the question at first glance hence, they used modelling as an avenue to comprehend the leading question of the problem.

I didn't know what to do at first because I was slightly confused. Instead, I drew to understand the problem you asked us to answer. After drawing it, I saw that if you combine angles GLK and KLJ, you will get 180 degrees. Thus, I was able to create a formula, which was $180 = x + 128 + x + 48$. The value of x was needed to be found first in order to solve for the degrees of angles GLK and KLJ. (S9.2)

1.1.2. Identifying and Determining Concepts and Information

Identifying and determining concepts and information were other techniques used by the learners to solve the given word problem. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as identifying mathematical concepts and determining the needed information and approaches.

1.1.2.1. Identifying Key Mathematical Concepts

This elaborated metacognitive strategies utilized by learners' presents how students put an emphasis on identifying key mathematical concepts in the problem to understand what the whole task means. S1.1, S1.3, and S1.4 mentioned some key mathematical concepts during the interview sessions that made them understand what the whole problem meant. S1.1 and S1.4 said that the problem tackled the distance between two points and their cue was the given coordinate system which were the x and y coordinates. S1.3 elaborated their assumption that by plotting the given points represented by the four grade 10 students one will be able to form lines such as vertical, horizontal, or slant lines, which can be the basis on what formula to be used.

Similarly, S2.1, S2.3, and S2.4, the students of T2 and both of whom were solving the same problem, were able to identify the key mathematical terms intended for the problem. S2.1 said that the problem was all about distance between two points and its main goal was to find the distance between the four given points represented by houses of the four grade 10 students.

On the other hand, all the four students of T3 mentioned during their interviews the concepts of the word problem pertaining to central angle, inscribed angle, and their intercepted arcs. S3.1 and S3.4 identified that the measurement of a central angle was equal to the measurement of its intercepted arc while the measure of the inscribed angle was half the measure of the intercepted arc and the degrees of the whole circle was 360 while half of it was 180 degrees.

In addition, S3.2 mentioned that in order to determine the value of the central angle and intercepted arc, the value of the equation (x) needed to be identified first.

Of course, the given angle measurement surely comes along with an x variable, which means, you have to know the true value of x in order to determine the correct measurement of the angle or the intercepted {angle}. (S3.2)

Similarly, S3.3, S4.3, and S4.5 defined that when two straight lines cross a circle the part of the circle between the intersection points is called the intercepted arc. At first glance, S7.1, S7.3, and S7.4 of T7 already recognized that the given word problem talked about the measurement of the central angle and its intercepted arc. Two reasons for S7.1 were first, the vertex of the given angle was in the center and second, the familiarity of the given problem to the examples they answered during online sessions.

At any rate, S8.1 and S8.4 of T8 mentioned that the given problem required learners to find the length of the diameter of the circle given its two endpoints attached at the circumference of the circle. This kind of idea gave S8.4 that the concept was all about distance formulas or finding the distance between two points.

Moreover, S9.1 and S9.3 of T9 defined that the measure of an inscribed angle was half the measure of the intercepted arc while the measure of the central angle was equal to the measure of the intercepted arc. Having said that, S11.1 and S11.2 of T11 mentioned that the given problem was all about determining the distance between two points whereas according to S11.4, plotting and graphing the points of the given problem would create a right triangle composed of vertical line, horizontal line, and slant line which required different formulae.

At last, S12.2 and S12.4 of T12 who were given a problem about central angle and its intercepted arc mentioned that in order to get the final answer in the problem first, they needed to get the value of the equation [x].

1.1.2.2. Determining the Needed Informatio

This elaborating metacognitive strategy emphasizes the utilization of determining the needed information to solve the given problem. S1.2 and S1.4, both students of T1, were able to determine the needed information and remember the process on how to solve the given word problem during the interview session. S1.2 said that if one were to plot the points in the Cartesian plane, a number of right triangles may be formed. Having said that, the formula to be used for the solving process depends on the kind of line that would be formed when connecting the points.

In a similar way, S2.1 and S2.3 of T2 who received the same problem as the students of T1 said that by locating the given points in the rectangular coordinate system, it was possible and easy for them to determine the distances between these points.

I was able to understand the sample problem by determining the given, which, in this problem, were points. So, these points were to be located using the rectangular coordinate system to identify their distances. (S2.1)

In another way, S4.2 pointed out that he needed to look for the measurement of angle GLK and angle KLJ hence, theorems of central angle were the needed information for the problem he received. Meanwhile, S5.1 and S5.4 of T5 noticed that the problem talked about the measurement of the diameter of a circle given its points hence, S5.4 affirmed that the information needed to solve the problem was the concept of distance formula.

Subsequently, S6.1, S6.3, and S6.4 of T6 received a problem about central angle and its intercepted arc and cited that the theorem along with these topics must be needed in order to understand how to approach this task. S6.1 added that the familiarity of the problem helped him to remember the topic which led him to think about the theorem involved in the subject matter.

However, S7.1 enumerated the different processes that he needed to undergo to solve the given problem. Based on the transcript of the interview, he indicated that by using the given problem, the first thing he would do was to write the given, make an illustration, prepare the appropriate equation, and finally implement the solution.

Similarly, S7.2 and S7.4 of T7 were able to recall the theorem indicated in the problem about the central angle and its intercepted arc. S7.2 mentioned that this problem required an equation to find the value of x before getting the measures of the angle and intercepted arc. He also stated that in order to solve the problem, he needed to read it well, identify the given, determine what was asked and figure out the required formula.

On the other hand, S8.1 and S8.2 revealed that the problem they received during the interviews was about distance between two points, which, according to S8.1, led to the question about the distance of the houses of the four grade 10 students whose main sort of option was to determine the formula to be used depending on the kind of line formed whether vertical, horizontal, or slant.

Apparently, S9.2 of T9, S10.1, S10.2, and S10.3 of T10 believed that the way to identify the needed information in the given problem was through plotting points in the Cartesian plane. S10.3 commended that using these points plotted in the x - y plane would be easy to determine the formula to be used and the needed approach to be employed, which depended on the kind of line that would be formed.

Finally, S11.4 of T11, S12.2, and S12.3 of T12 used to highlight the given in order to identify the information needed to solve the central angle and intercepted arc. S12.3 said that she needed to identify first the equation needed in the problem to find the x to make

it easy for her to solve the other missing measurement.

In summary, students were able to demonstrate most of the attributions on the declarative knowledge of cognition. Most of the learners were able to read and reread the problem, determine the needed information to understand it, and comprehend the lead question as their techniques to understand the task while only few learners used translation to get the idea of the problem. Generally, in this portion, students used to have a cue of terms on the problem to determine what the problem was all about by reading, recalling, and translating. In addition, they were able to determine math concepts and needed information because of the problem's familiarity.

How do learners understand the problem is central to exploring the factual knowledge the learner needs before being able to process concepts related to the topic. It also refers to knowing about or what, the knowledge of one's skills, intellectual resources, and abilities as a learner. At certain instances, the following were probed from the learners: reading and recalling the lesson, translating concepts, understanding the lead question, identifying mathematical concepts, and determining the needed information. Generally, learners' declarative knowledge was directed towards knowing "the about" of things (Akin et al., 2007) and such knowledge was expanded to learners' know-how about the life and issues revolving it (Yildiz et al., 2009).

2.1 Learners' Procedural Knowledge

From the data on procedural knowledge, substituting, representing, and organizing solutions emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers utilized by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated by the implications of specific metacognitive strategies such as using substitution while solving, using representation while solving, and organizing solutions coherently and logically.

1.2.1. Substituting, Representing, and Organizing Solutions

Substituting, representing, and organizing solutions were the metacognitive strategies used by the learners in solving word problems. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as substitution process, use of representation while solving, and organizing of solution coherently and logically.

1.2.1.1. Using Substitution While Solving

Although most of the learners made substitutions during the process of solving the problem since all the problems required formula or an equation, yet only three of them were able to mention this process during the interview session. S1.1, S2.4, and S5.2 were the three students who were able to mention that they used substitution to distribute the given to the required formula during the procedural activity. Although it was known already that this was an automatic response in solving a problem, still, careful substitution must be made especially in congruence with the given of the problem, hence labelling the given must be parallel to the required formula so that during substitution, mistakes and errors would be avoided.

After I determined the formula to be used for the solution process, I employed a substitution process after labeling all the given that I saw present in the problem you gave us so as to distribute them. // I employed a substitution process to distribute all the given that I saw present in the problem you gave us after labeling them.] (S1.1)

1.2.1.2. Using Representation while Solving

This was based on how they understood the procedure or how they drew due to the hesitation they felt while doing the procedure. In terms of representing the problem, S1.1 and S2.3 used illustration to model the problem as part of their procedure. S1.1 stated that he drew the figure in the problem by graphing the plotted points. S2.3 did the same as S1.1 to visualize the line formed by the two dots and to see if the formula he was using while solving the problem was correct.

Similarly, S6.1 and S6.2 drew a circle and labelled the given data to see the illustration and checked the equation used to determine how to process the given task.

I drew a circle first and then I wrote the given in the problem to see how I would solve it. (S6.2)

On the other hand, S7.3, S9.2, and S9.3 also used representation as parts of their procedure. S7.3 mentioned that he drew a circle and put the given. He saw that arc KJ as the given was equal to angle KLJ and also equal to $x+48$. He thought that when he added KLJ and angle GLK, he would get a total of 180 degrees which was also equivalent to a semi-circle. The same was true with S9.2 and S9.3 who also drew a circle and added angle KLJ and angle GLK to come up with an equation equal to $180 = x + 128 + x + 48$.

Moreover, S8.2 sketched the graph and plotted the points of the given to understand the problem and determine if the formula he was using was appropriate for the available data. In addition, S11.1 and S11.2 sketched the graph of the problem they had while solving the problem. During the solving process, S11.2 was confused about her work that led her to decide to draw the illustration to make an assurance with the formula she was using in the problem. Furthermore, since the problem was about central angle and intercepted arc, it didn't have a specific formula, S12.1 and S12.2 made a representation to visualize the image with the data and to analyze the equation suited to solve the given problem.

1.2.1.3. Organizing Solution Coherently and Logically.

All the students who underwent an interview were able to discuss how they organized their solutions coherently and logically. S1.1 stated that he just followed the steps taught to them during their online class. He said that the first thing he made was to highlight the given and to write them below the problem with proper labelling. The second thing was he comprehended the leading question to be able to illustrate the information available in the problem. After graphing, he identified the formula to be used, which was the distance formula and used substitution to change the variables from the given data. In performing the operations, he followed PEMDAS (Parenthesis, Equation, Multiplication or Division, Addition or Subtraction) and ended with his final answer.

At the same time, all the student-participants in this study were able to mention that they used a specific formula based on what the problem needed. It showed from this study that familiarity to the problem contributed significantly to how students approached the given problem. In this section, the researcher decided to present only a few and significant responses from the interviews.

For instance, S1.2 used an appropriate technique to organize his solution to the given word problem about the distance between two points. Based on the evaluation of the researcher, S1.2 was able to use specific formulas needed to solve a particular problem e.g., horizontal, vertical, and slant line formulae. Below were the responses of the selected participants based on the three questions from the interviews.

The first question was composed of five processing questions as mentioned in the methodologies. The problem started with the problem indicating the points of the four grade 10 students as representation of their respective houses. The first problem was to find the distance between Emilio and Gabriella's houses. The second was the distance between Jose and Emilio's houses. The third was the distance between Gabriella and Antonio's houses. The fourth was the formula to be used to find the distance between Antonio and Emilio's houses. The last one was the solution and answer in question number four. These questions are called processing questions and among the students who received these questions during the interview, S1.2 was one among those who presented his answer on how he was able to organize his work coherently and logically and at the same time read the formulae correctly.

The second question was about finding the measurement of angle GLK and angle KLJ given the measurement of angle GLK was equals to $x + 128$ and arc KJ which was equal to $x + 48$ in circle L. Among the students who received this problem during the interview, S4.2 was one of those who rigorously presented her ideas coherently and logically.

The first thing I did was to find the x as we all know that the total measurement of a circle is 360 degrees and in order to get the diameter of the circle, the equivalent is 180 degrees. For the angle GLK, the given provided was x plus 128 degrees and as for the arc KJ, the given was x plus 48 degrees which was also equivalent to angle KLJ if the theorem between central angle and intercepted arc was to be recalled.

So, what I did to obtain the answer was, uhm, {to solve} 180 degrees is equal to x plus 128 degrees plus x plus 48 degrees—this was the formula I came up with when I drew it. The second step I did was to add the two x 's with which I got $2x$. After that, I added 128 degrees and 48 degrees and the answer I got is 176 degrees and so, 180 degrees is equal to $2x$ plus 176 degrees. To get the value of x , I had to transpose 176 degrees so from positive, it became negative. 180 degrees minus 176 degrees is equal to 4 is equal to $2x$. For 2 to be cancelled, it had to be divided by 2 so 4 divided by 2 is equal to 2, and so the value of x is 2.

So, the answer to the question as to what the measurement of angle GLK was to change the x to 2 based on the equation $x + 128$ and so we have $2 + 128$ equals 130 degrees for angle GLK. The second question was about the measurement of angle KLJ which is $x + 48$ wherein once you change x to 3, you will get 50 degrees as the answer.

The last question was about finding the length of the diameter of the circle given its two points [point A and point B]. One of the learners who received this question was S8.4 who presented her ideas well during the interview.

I first substituted it to the formula provided which is d equals square root of quantity x sub 2 minus x sub 1 plus quantity y sub 2 minus y sub 1. The given for x is 14, 8 for y_2 , 2 for x_1 , and 3 for y_1 . After that, I subtracted 14 and 2 equals positive 12 then 8 minus 3 equals positive 5. I then squared 12 which became 144 and then 5 which turned to 25. The total is 144 plus 25 which then equals to 169. I then needed to get the square root, which then led me to 13 units. So, the length of the diameter of the given circle is 13 units. (S8.4)

In summary, the students were able to showcase the organizing process but least on the attribution to substitution. They were able to use representation while solving the problem to see if they are on the right track, be able to use substitution as part of the solving process, and be able to organize their solution coherently and logically. The second main question points at the procedural knowledge inquiring learners' description about their mathematics learning technique/s. Their answers centered on developing procedural knowledge or the knowledge manifested when learners complete a procedure or process based on purposes.

The learner's mindfulness on how to implement learning strategies exhibits one's procedural knowledge. The learners' responses on how they implement determined learning strategies may be typified similar to what Glaser (2000, in Baxter, 2016) refers to as agency for learning. An instructional psychologist, Robert Glaser, provided a prominent revolution in the theories of learning and cognition. Centrally, the answers are clustered into a sole theme, which was the substituting, representing, and organizing solutions.

1.3. Learners' Conditional Knowledge

From the data on conditional knowledge, questioning the problem and own practices and generating solutions emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers utilized by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated by the implications of specific metacognitive strategies such as questioning the problem, consistent practices to develop familiarity, identifying appropriate solution, and exploring alternative solutions.

1.3.1. Questioning the Problem and Own Practices

Questioning the problem and even student's own practices were the techniques used by the students to identify what formula suited the given problem, what went wrong and what went right, and when and why to use such strategies, techniques, or approach in solving the problem.

1.3.1.1. Questioning the Problem

S1.1 said that upon seeing the problem, he generated questions on how to approach the problem and as to what process or procedure would be used. S1.3 added that he asked himself some questions on what to do to answer the problem and as to what formula was needed for each question. Similar to S1.1, he found that visualizing or modelling the problem would help him see the process clearly. In addition, S1.4 asked himself questions about the formula but when he saw the slant line formed from the graph that he made, he used distance formula as the source to find the answer in the given word problem.

At first, I asked myself what formula I will use. After plotting it on the graph, I saw that it is a slant line, and so I said, "if the given is a slant line, it means that distance formula should be used." That was how I thought of it. (S1.4)

S2.3, on the other hand, thought at first how he would be going to approach the problem. His options were to graph or plot first the given and think of what would be the best technique for this because he knew that the formula depended on the kind of line formed between two points.

S4.2 did the same thing as S2.3. He stated that he listened well to his teacher during their online discussion yet he was still unsure on how to do the problem hence, he made modelling and labelling the problem his avenue to generate questions about the equation that was suited to the problem since it did not have the specific formula. The same was true with S4.3 who was unsure of his procedure after solving the problem that made him ask himself if he was doing it correctly or not. Finally, S4.4 asked some questions about his procedures and final answer.

S5.2 questioned the problem if it was referring to the distance between two points. He was so unsure at first since the problem required him to find the length of the diameter of the circle given its two points. The same was true with S6.4 who thought of how to solve the problem he received and how to arrive at the correct solution until such time that he decided to represent the given through drawing a circle and therefore was able to determine the angle GLJ was equal to 180 degrees and it was equal to the sum of angle GLK and angle KLJ. Finally, S7.1, similar to S5.2 and S6.4, generated question as to what process and what formula would she be using to obtain her final answer.

S8.1, S8.3, and S8.4 of T8 revealed that they also generated questions in solving the given word problem. S8.4 stated that at first, she was thinking on what specific formula or what steps would be used to operate the problem. When she plotted the given points on the Cartesian plane, she saw different lines [horizontal, vertical, and slant] and when she connected the two points, it made her think as to what formula she would be using for each kind of line.

Finally, S11.2, S12.2, and S12.3 used to sketch the given to visualize the problem. S11.2 said that she would sometimes get confused upon distinguishing the value of x and y coordinates. On the other hand, S12.3 was so uncertain of her answer because her problem didn't have a specific formula which meant that it needed proper analysis to come up with a correct solution and answer.

1.3.1.2. Consistent Practice to Develop Familiarity

S2.3 mentioned that her familiarity to the problem helped her to identify the appropriate procedures to be used in solving the task. Also, S3.1 used variable x as a cue or hint to solve the given problem in view of the fact that it was similar to what his teacher taught them during their online discussion while S4.4 found out what technique was appropriate since his teacher taught the same topic to them. On the other hand, S5.1 was so confident in his procedure since he listened well to his teacher's discussion. S5.3 stated that the given problem required a distance formula and was very much alike with his previously learned problem. Finally, S5.2 revealed that the problem talked about the distance of the two given points.

All the four students of T6, on the other hand, used the familiarity of the problem to identify the required formula. S6.2 thought of the steps to be used in the problem. S6.3 said that the problem was familiar but not as exact as the given samples in the online class discussion. In addition, S6.4 considered the importance of familiarity in solving the problem.

Yes, the familiarity of the problem helped. It was like I had seen the examples you gave us with the ones {my teacher/sir} provided during discussions. (S6.1)

Additionally, S7.2 and S7.4 of T7 mentioned how familiarity helped them in understanding the given word problem. S8.2 also revealed that his familiarity with the problem made it easy for him to solve the problem. Lastly, S9.3 appreciated the importance of being familiar with a similar problem since it would help one to identify what process or procedure to use and how to do it properly.

S10.4 mentioned that upon seeing the problem, he already knew what to do. S11.3 and S12.4 agreed with the statement of S10.4 and found the hint when the length was missing and given its two points, a distance formula was used. Furthermore, S12.1 recalled that he was asked to recite during the online class session which in turn gave him the opportunity to remember the process and the problem.

On the other hand, S1.1 was very confident to say that he had no questions about the problem as he was with his answer. S1.2 said that he was satisfied with the way and process that he had learned and owned since his teacher also taught him another way to approach the given problem.

S2.3 said that familiarity helped him gain assurance with his answer while S2.4 mentioned that he followed the process carefully to determine the formula and the given by analyzing the problem.

On the contrary, S3.1 revealed her assurance with her answer and solution that before undergoing the interview, she already had an idea about the topic due to familiarity of the problem to her and on how to solve the algebraic expression. She also added that her checking process made her more confident in arriving at a similar answer with her first procedure.

Moreover, S3.3 confidently said that she answered the problem within two minutes since, according to her, the problem was so easy and similar but not totally the same from her teacher's example during online class session.

1.3.2. Generating Solutions

Generating solutions was another technique used by the learners in conditional knowledge. This elaborated metacognitive strategy offers learners to determine appropriate processes and explore alternative solutions.

1.3.2.1. Identifying Solution's Appropriateness

Using the given problem, S1.3 mentioned that she was able to understand it when she plotted the points on the graph. She said that when she graphed the points she noticed the missing part hence, it made it easy for her to solve the problem. In addition, S3.2 and S3.4 thought of a procedure that they could use to solve the given word problem. S3.2 mentioned that the solution should start from looking for the value of x to be able to determine the values of the two missing angles.

S4.1 and S4.2 hesitated about the solution they did. They both asked themselves during the interview as to what procedure fitted the given problem. S4.2 asked how to start the solution after he drew and labelled the problem's representation because he was unsure if his thinking was correct.

S6.3 looked for an equation that could be used to solve the given problem. Although all of them who received this kind of problem did the same, S6.3 was one among the students who mentioned during the interview that he thought of an equation to approach the given problem.

I was thinking how to solve for x since there was no provided formula. I then realized that when all the given were combined based on the figure I drew/made, it would reach 180 degree and so I came up with the equation $180 = x + 128 + x + 48$. (S6.3)

S7.1 thought of the different procedures he learned from his teacher while S7.3 said that he thought first of the theorem about the central angle and intercepted arc, which helped him create an equation suited to the given problem. In a similar way, S8.2 and S8.4 mentioned that they first looked for the line formed from the given points to determine the appropriate formula to be used in the problem.

Based on the given points, I figured out the appropriate what formula to use based on the lines created through the points given in the problem using Cartesian plane.] (S8.2)

S9.2 revealed that he already knew the procedure upon receiving the problem. Familiarity helped him determine the process. When he tried to draw its illustration with a semi-circle, he figured out how to create the needed equation to find the value of x since a semi-circle was equal to 180 degrees. S11.1 agreed with this, saying that familiarity contributed significantly to how they approached the problem.

1.3.2.2. Exploring Possible Solutions

S1.4 of T1 revealed that upon viewing the slant line formed after he graphed the points, it gave him an idea that distance formula would be the required formula to be used in the given problem.

At first, I asked myself what formula I will use. After plotting it on the graph, I saw that it is a slant line, and so I said, "if the given is a slant line, it means that distance formula should be used." That was how I thought of it. (S1.4)

Similarly, S4.4, S5.1, and S5.4 used the word distance in the problem to determine that this referred to the distance between two points.

To identify what particular formula to be used, they plotted the given points in the Cartesian plane and graphed them forming horizontal, vertical, and slant lines. Each line required a different procedure to follow hence, it was better to determine first what kind of line was in the problem, S5.4 added.

S6.1 revealed during his interview that he knew when to use the formula since he still remembered what his teacher taught to him. On the other hand, S7.2 and S7.4 agreed that the secret to identifying the formula in a problem was to understand the problem first and its leading question. S7.2 mentioned that in order to determine the formula or equation in the problem. He tried first to recall the theorem between the central angle and intercepted arc.

In like manner to S1.4, S8.1 said that in order to determine the formula on the problem, he needed to graph first the given points because the formula depended on the kind of lines that would appear.

Furthermore, S10.1, S10.2, S10.3, S11.4, and S12.1 were confident as to when to use the formula. In an interview, S10.1 mentioned that if the x variables of the two given points were the same, he would use the vertical line formula. If the y variables of the two given points were the same, horizontal line formula would be applicable; and if no variables were the same that meant that the line was slant and distance formula was required.

On the other hand, S1.1, S1.2, and S1.3 thought of other ways on how to solve the problem given to them. Students would tend to do this as an avenue to check if their answer in the first solution was correct. S1.1 said that he used Pythagorean Theorem as an alternative solution to see if his first answer was correct. S1.4 asked himself if there was another way to approach the problem thus, also arriving at the same thinking as S1.1. S1.2 thought about the way of counting the points in the graph, whether it was horizontal or vertical, and applied Pythagorean Theorem. S2.2 believed that finding another way to solve the problem could help him check his final answer.

The same was true with S3.4 and S4.4 who thought of ways on how to approach the given problem. During the process, S3.4 figured out ways on how to approach his problem to get the values of the given questions in the interview.

Finally, S5.4 and S7.2 stated that upon receiving the problem on the interview, they came up with ways on how to approach the given problem or how to start the process. S7.2 added that it was really important for him to plan first when he used the given and the formula and study how to use them before he would start with the procedure

In summary, students used more techniques in conditional knowledge in terms of questioning the process and their own practices and generating solutions. Students question the problem in order to think of the different ways on how to solve and process the given. They affirmed that consistent practice given by the teacher would help them to understand the problem, generate questions about the problem as to what and why to use such strategy which enable them to develop their awareness towards the problem. Also, it was mentioned that labelling and illustrating problem specifics help them to determine appropriate solutions to the problem and be able to explore possible solutions.

The learner's conditional knowledge consists apparently of determining under what circumstances specific processes or skills should transfer (Kirbulut, 2014). It is the knowledge about when and why to use learning procedures or the application of declarative and procedural knowledge with certain conditions presented. The research posited on the learners' usefulness and strengths in mathematics learning and their motivation to study mathematics. Since conditional knowledge is an extant, a specific situation on the use of learning strategies was asked as well as the rationale in choosing such strategy.

2. Learners Regulation of Cognition

Learners' regulation of cognition using its three metacognitive factors (planning, monitoring, and evaluating) emerged through a specific metacognitive strategy such breaking down, illustrating, and labelling, thinking about the information, formula, and steps, making sense on owns work, verifying solutions, reviewing the process, and revising and drawing conclusion.

2.1. Learners' Planning Regulation

From the data on planning, breaking down, illustrating, and labelling and thinking about the information, formula, and steps emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers utilized by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated by the implications of specific metacognitive strategies such as breaking down the problem, illustrating and labelling concepts, writing down information, determining required formulas, and thinking about steps.

2.1.1. Breaking Down, Illustrating, and Labelling

Through breaking down its parts, illustrating figures, drawing, graphing, and labelling helped the learners to understand the problem, visualize it, and see its missing parts. It also aided them to decide what formula was needed, to figure out the context of the task, and to see the bigger picture of the problem.

2.1.1.1. Breaking down the Problem

This elaborating metacognitive strategy utilized by learners presents an emphasis on analyzing the problem. This pertains to breaking down the problem into parts to understand the whole thing. S1.1 mentioned that he divided the problem into parts so that he could

focus on the end question since the problem was composed of five processing questions.

In relation to this, S4.4 stated that he imagined the circle first. Since the circle was equal to 360 degrees hence, angle GLJ was 180 degrees since it represented the half of the circle or the diameter of the circle. He thought that if he added angle GLK and angle KLJ, he would get angle GLJ as the sum of the two given angles. Similar to S4.4, S6.1 and S6.2 did the same way of analyzing the problem about the central angle and intercepted arc as part of their procedural process.

In addition, S7.1, S7.2, S7.3, and S9.1 analyze the problem first before proceeding to solve it. According to S7.1, the given circle had two given angles that when combined would create a total of 180 degrees equivalent to the measurement of a semicircle. Also, S7.2 said that the idea of the central angle and intercepted arc was needed to understand the given problem.

All the four students of T10 mentioned during the individual interview that they analyzed the problem beforehand as part of the procedural process. The problem given to them was about the distance between two points.

Furthermore, S12.2 and S12.3 stated that in order to solve the problem, one needed to understand first the leading question, the requirements needed, and the missing portion. These things would help in making the procedural process systematic and would give one more assurance in solving the problem.

2.1.1.2. Illustrating and Labelling Concepts

Emphasis on drawing pertains to how students illustrate, represent, and visualize their ideas in order to understand the given problem. All the four students of T1 [S1.1, S1.2, S1.3, S1.4] gave a remark about the importance of visualizing as one of processes of understanding the problem. S1.1 stated that drawing the problem helped him understand the task and gave him knowledge on how to solve it. He sketched a graph for the given four points to determine as well the kind of line it will reveal in order to decide the formula to be used in solving the problem.

Likewise, S2.3 and S2.4 mentioned that graphing the given points on the Cartesian plane would provide an avenue to what line would be formed and to what formula would be used. On the contrary, S3.2 and S3.4 of T3 said during the interview that in order to determine the equation of the given problem for central angle and intercepted arc, one needed to draw a circle, put the given angles and visualize to see if the given was actually the diameter of the circle which measures 180 degrees.

I drew a circle to know what were needed. Uhm, yes, there was if you visualized the given illustration, you would see it on the line. (S3.2)

Similarly, S4.1, S4.2, and S4.4 of T4 drew their ideas about the problem similar to what S3.2 did. S4.4 said that he drew a circle to see the appearance of the figure when the given was already labelled. He believed that this could be a way to think how he will approach the given task.

S5.2 and S5.4 portrayed the technique of their teacher as they analyzed the given word problem. They used a graph to plot the points and draw a line. The decision of the four students of T6, S7.4, S8.2, and S8.4 depended on the results of the illustration they had made to visualize the structure of the problem. The problem given to S6.1, S6.2, S6.3, S6.4, and S7.4 was all about central angle and intercepted arc where they drew the figure of the circle to see the relationship of each given and to conclude an equation that happened to be the avenue to determine the measures of angles GLK and KLJ. Evidently, S8.2 and S8.4 plotted the given four points on the rectangular coordinate system to determine the lines formed from these four points and to decide as to what formula they would be using.

The strategy I did to make the problem easier to solve was to sketch a graph first. I then plotted the points so I would know what formula to use—either slant, horizontal, or vertical formula. Pythagorean Theorem could also be used. (S8.2)

S9.2 and S9.3 mentioned during the interview that the first thing they made was to write the given problem which were $x+128$ and $x+48$ represented by angle GLK and angle KLJ. S9.2 elaborated that she drew a circle and put the letters forming a semi-circle equivalent to 180 degrees. Hence, this made her decision to come up with the equation $180 = x + 128 + x + 48$ as her basis to solve for the value of x and to find the measures of the two angles [angle GLK and angle KLJ].

S10.1, S10.2, and S10.4 stated during the individual interview that all of them were able to draw an illustration to represent the problem. S10.1 narrated that she started the problem through reading and upon seeing the problem she mentioned that she thought about the rectangular coordinate plane to plot the given points, and to see and to think of what suited formula to use to each of the questions. She added that upon graphing and connecting the values of the given word problem, the figure formed a square. She acknowledged that the questions given in the problem were in sequence to guide her in arriving at the final answer.

The easiest way for the four students of T11 to analyze the problem given was summed up through visualizing the concept, as stated during their individual interview. This idea led them to graph the given using the Cartesian plane and to see what figure would be formed. S11.2 mentioned that distinguishing x and y coordinates would sometimes lead her to confusion due to unfamiliarity. Which mostly happened while understanding the graphing process. S11.4 said that upon connecting the two lines from the given problem on determining the length of the diameter of a circle given its two points revealed that it was a slant line which required a distance formula.

Finally, S12.1, S12.2, and S12.4 mentioned that they also drew a figure to understand the problem and to prepare a plan on how to approach it. S12.1 at first was unsure about his understanding of the problem which, consequently, opted to draw a circle and put the given angle GLK, arc KJ, and angle GLJ. After he drew the figure GLK and arc KJ, which were actually the same as angle KLJ, he noticed that they were equivalent to angle GLJ forming the half of a circle.

On the other hand, S1.3 mentioned that he labelled the four grade 10 students using the first letter of their names e.g., Emilio as point E, Antonio as point A, Gabriella as point G, and Jose as point J. S2.1 acknowledged during the one-on-one interview that all the given points of the problem presented to her belonged to quadrant one, which she made as her focused quadrant when she labelled the given on the Cartesian plane.

S3.1 stated that he drew the circle and labelled the given points from the angle GLK and KLJ e.g., point G, point L, point J and point K.

I drew a circle after that and put all the given for me to better understand what needs to be done. I noticed that when I combined angle GLK and angle KLJ, I was able to come up with angle GLJ which was equal to the diameter of the circle. I labelled four points here like point G, point L, point J, and point K and afterwards named the center as point P. (S3.1)

Lastly, S4.1 labelled the given as angle GLK equals $x+128$ and angle KLJ equals $x+48$. From this, he was able to see the equation intended to solve the given task which was $180 = x+128 + x+48$.

2.1.2. Thinking about the Information, Formula, and Steps

Thinking about the information, formula, and steps gave the learners a chance to select the operation intended or necessary for a given problem and at the same time made decisions on the best path on how to set up the given word problem. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as writing down the needed information, determining the required formula, and thinking about all the necessary steps to solve the given task.

2.1.2.1. Writing Down of Information

One of the important factors in planning was regarding how students organized the materials about the problem. Putting emphasis on how students write down the information needed to solve the problem would give them an avenue on how they would arrange the materials that were needed to undertake the given task. S1.4 mentioned during his interview that writing the given would prevent him from confusion. He also said that he used representation to each point as his guide when he plotted the points on the coordinate system he drew.

In a similar manner, S2.2 used to connect the given to each question to understand the problem and S3.2 and S3.3 believed that organization of materials was very important before solving a problem. S3.2 said that when solving, one needed to have a set of steps to follow to arrange the materials. She added that to solve the given problem, she needed to find first the value of x of the equation which largely depended on the given value which were x plus 128 degrees and x plus 48 degrees.

Similar to S2.2, S4.1, S5.2, S5.2, and S5.3 also wrote the given information of the problem on a piece of paper and thought of the formula suited to the given word problem. S5.3 mentioned that he used representation to write the given such as x sub 1 equals 14, x sub 2 equals 2, y sub 1 equals 3 and y sub 2 equals 8.

On the other hand, S6.1, S 6.3, and S6.4 wrote the given of the problem they received during their individual interview. S6.3 said that from Circle L, the given angle GLK equals $x+128$, arc KJ equals $x+48$ and angle GLJ which was equal to 180 degrees.

Similar to the students of T6, S7.2 identified the given word problem before solving. S8.1 and S8.4 of T8 stated that they highlighted the given in the problem before they wrote them. Also, S8.4 mentioned that writing the given depended mainly on the question. Since there were a sequence of five questions in the given problem, writing the given problem was the technique she considered.

Comparatively, S9.1, S9.2, S12.2, and S12.3 also wrote the given word problem during their interviews similar to what they had learned from their teacher during their online session.

I just followed how it was taught to us, like I had to write first the given, such as the angle GLK which was $x + 128$ and angle KLJ which was $x + 48$. (S12.3)

2.1.2.2. Determining the Required Formula

Determining what formula will be possible for a kind of problem will be the focal point of this subtheme. Students of T1 – S1.2 and S1.4 - said that they used the formulae they learned from their past lesson, specifically the formula in slant line, horizontal line, and vertical line, because each from the five given questions in the problem required different formula hence, the formula to be used would depend on the kind of given they had. For instance, S1.4 mentioned that in point A the given coordinates were 14 and 8 and for point B the coordinates were 2 and 3. He said that since the two ordered pairs did not have common values, the slant line or the distance formula was the applicable one to use.

S3.1 and S3.3 stated that the procedure they used was the procedure they had learned from their teacher during the online session. S3.1

said that the first thing he did was to identify if the given could provide a whole circle or a half circle. From the given, he was able to form the equation to be used in order to solve the problem since no specific formula was required to solve the missing parts of the circle.

Similar to S1.2 and S1.4, S5.3 and S5.4 mentioned that the formula they used to solve the problem was the slant line formula, also known as distance formula, since no two given values for x and y were similar.

The formula used here was the distance formula since the line of the points was slant and therefore bore no similar value for x and y . (S5.4)

In contrast, S7.2 and 8.3 mentioned that they drew the given circle to identify the question they would be using for the problem. S7.2 stated that when angle GLK and KLJ were combined they would form angle GLJ which was equivalent to the diameter of the circle thus making angle GLJ equal to the sum of angle GLK and KLJ.

I drew a circle and then put angles GLK and KJL inside it. I realized that when they were combined, we could create angle GLJ which was equal to the diameter of the circle. So, GLJ was equals to GKL + KLJ. (S7.2)

Apparently, S10.3 said that his formula depended on the line formed when connecting points on the graph. He mentioned that he would use the vertical line formula for a vertical line and the same was true for a horizontal line. However, if the line was slant, he would then use the distance formula. Linked to S7.2, S12.3 used to combine the two given central angles to form an equation equivalent to 180 degrees.

2.1.2.3. Thinking about Steps

This puts an emphasis on how students think about all the steps before solving the problem as part of their plan for their learning activities. During the interview, the four students of T1 [S1.1, S1.2, S1.3, and S1.4] thought about the steps that they previously learned in their lesson regarding distance between two points.

First, I thought of how sir taught it to us last time during the discussion. I then recalled how I would write all the given. Second, I identified if x and y coordinates had the same value. Lastly, I thought of the formula that could be used for the problem. (S1.4)

Similar to the four students of T1, S2.3 and S2.4 of T2 mentioned during the interview the following steps they had gone through to solve the given word problem. S2.3 stated that the first step she made to come up with her answer was through drawing the rectangular coordinate system to locate the points and her second step was to determine the line formed from the graph of two points whether it is horizontal, vertical, or slant line. The third step was about substituting the given based on the formula and making a conclusion as the last step.

Akin to S2.3, S3.1 and S3.4 of T3 used to analyze the problem first as their technique in thinking about all the steps based on the given in the problem since it had no specific formula and the approach would depend on how they understood the theorem related to central angle and its intercepted arc. S3.1 stated that his first move was to determine the given and to place them in circle L. He thought that his next move was to develop an equation related to the given.

S4.2 and S4.3 of T4 stated that in order to solve the problem, the first thing to do was to find the x of the equation which could be drawn from the given problem by recalling what was taught by the teacher.

On the contrary, S6.1 and S6.2 of T6 mentioned about the familiarity of the problem which they used to remember how their teacher solved the problem.

Yes, there were steps that I followed. I did so based on how they were discussed to us, that is to follow the easier, clearer, and similar way to what was told us. I then recalled the steps I had to do since the problem you gave us seemed familiar to that of the problems given by sir during the discussion last time. (S6.2)

Finally, S7.1 and S7.2 stated during their individual interview that they followed certain steps to solve the given word problem. S7.2 mentioned that he planned to read the problem well to identify the given, to know what was asked, and to identify the formula. Prior to that, however, all done in a similar fashion as what his teacher did during the online class, he indicated that in finalizing his answer, he solved the problem on a different sheet of paper on a trial-and-error basis and ought to start where he could be comfortable in solving.

To conclude, most of the learners were able to demonstrate the illustration of the problem, particularly through graphing and drawing figures as well as determining the intended formula in the problem but less emphasis was put on the importance of labelling in solving the problem. Generally, in this portion, students showcased modal attribution towards breaking down, illustrating, and labelling techniques while few attributions were made from thinking about the information, formula, and steps.

Planning, goal setting, and allocating resources prior to learning as well as learner's devotion in studying mathematics contributed greatly in the planning regulation of cognition. This facet also involves diagnosis organization towards accomplishing a goal. Congruently, what were revealed from the learners' answers could be categorized into several advantages that learners gained out of

simply planning.

Planning as a strategy capacitates the learner to be ready in facing a multitude of academic tasks. Hence, as a strategy, it is central to what learners do before, during, and after a learning task. According to Teo and Bergin (2009), the careful use of available strategies for learning, including the learners' organization of study materials, covers what planning is all about.

2.2. Learners' Monitoring Regulation

From the data on monitoring, making sense of one's own work and verifying solutions emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers utilized by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated by the implications of specific metacognitive strategies such as providing second thoughts, recognizing errors, familiarity with the problem, checking work step by step, reflecting from time to time, and using scratch to draft a solution.

2.2.1. Making Sense on Owns Work

Making sense of their own work was one among the techniques used by the students while solving the word problem. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as providing second thoughts, recognition of errors and familiarity of the problem, which helps learners to better understand the solving process, to judge their thinking, to see errors before writing the final answer, and to be oriented whenever they encounter similar problems.

2.2.1.1. Providing a Second Thoughts

One of the signs that a student processed a monitoring skill was when he/she used to think twice about his procedures while solving a problem. S1.1 and S2.2 had similar reasons why they thought twice upon solving the given word problem during the one-on-one interview session. S2.2 doubted her solution or process. She was thinking twice if her work was the same as her teacher's solution. She wanted to be sure with her steps and procedure used in solving the distance between two points.

Yes, I had second thoughts since I would think whether what I was doing or whether the solution I was using in what our teacher taught us was right. (S2.2)

In like manner, S3.2 stated that she had to weigh up the problem while solving the central angle and intercepted arc. Her grounds created confusion in the interconnection of the lines and angles especially that she lacked mastery about the theorems involving the problem.

Apparently, S4.2 and S4.3 also hesitated when doing the process of solving a problem. According to S4.2, there were times when she thought if she was doing the process right or not, especially that her idea on operation of integers and addition property of equality led her to confusion while answering the problem.

At the same time, S5.1 and S5.4 hesitated about their answers, although correct, due to the confusion with the formula they were using. Also, S5.4 mentioned that he already forgot some parts of their previous lesson about distance between two points.

S8.2 and S8.4 students of T8 were also skeptical while solving the given word problem. S8.2 was uncertain while doing so. She explained that sometimes she would forget the integers under x coordinate and y coordinate while, on the other hand, S8.4 got confused about the formula he was using because horizontal line and vertical line formulas did not require square rooting. Finally, S9.2, S9.4, and S10.3 admitted that they had doubts in answering the given word problem because they found mathematics as a difficult subject.

2.2.1.2. Recognizing Errors

This portion of the research put an emphasis on how learners recognize their errors while solving the given word problem. Some errors made by the learners were through integers' signs, wrong estimation, and formula misconception.

During the interview, S1.3 stated that he was able to recognize the errors while doing the procedure on his problem regarding distance between two points. He forgot that the formula for horizontal lines had an absolute value which meant that there should be no negative answers in the problem. He felt so fortunate when he saw his mistake and from there, he admitted that he learned something based on the problem.

The same is true with S3.4. She stated that while solving the equation derived from the given measurement of central angle and intercepted arc, she felt confused about the transposition technique or from the addition of equality. Instead of writing 176 as negative, she wrote it as positive, which made her uneasy because she had big values as a result.

Similar to S3.4, S6.1 recognized his error in writing negative 176 to positive 176 which made her very confused with her answer since it was bigger than the degree of the given semi-circle. S6.1 added that he felt relieved when he changed the sign of 176 and was able to get the final answer.

I noticed that what I did first was wrong since I wrote down positive 176 instead of negative 176 and so it made me wonder why the answer, I arrived at was huge. It was much bigger than a half circle. Hahaha... and so I changed it. (S6.3)

S7.2 narrated that when he re-examined his solution, he was able to recognize the mistakes he made during the process of solving. He mentioned that instead of writing his answer from negative 176 when he transposed it [to the other side of the equation] along with the equal sign, he wrote it as positive. Moreover, instead of writing $2x$ for the sum of x plus x , he wrote x^2 . Fortunately, he was able to recognize those mistakes prior to getting the final answer.

Likewise, S8.1 also recognized the error she made during the solving process. She said that she made mistakes in question number three where she wrote negative seven instead of positive seven and forgot that the horizontal line formula had an absolute value symbol, which meant that no negative answers should occur. The same was true with S10.2, stating that she sometimes forgot to write the absolute value upon writing the formula.

Lastly, S11.1 of T11 made mistakes in writing the formula for the distance between two points. Instead of writing the addition sign for the operation of the difference between x coordinates and y coordinates, he wrote the minus sign. Luckily, he saw the mistakes or errors in the operation and immediately changed it before reaching or writing his final answer.

2.2.1.3. Familiarity on the Problem

This section put emphasis on the familiarity of the learners to the problem. They used this avenue to compare their works to similar problems and never felt any pressure and difficulty in solving the problem. S1.4 and S2.2, who received the same word problem said during the interview that they decided to use the distance formula to solve the word problem because it was similar to what their teachers taught them during their online session. S2.4 mentioned that he used the sample problem discussed during their virtual class to extract some ideas about the given problem in the interview on how to process the solution and on how to check his answer.

Using the sample problem in the last discussion, I was able to get an idea on how to solve the problem and how to check the process to see whether what I did was right or wrong. (S2.4)

On the other hand, S4.2 and S4.4 of T4 admitted that they used the sample made by their teachers to check if they were doing the right process. S5.3 added during the interview that the familiarity of the problem really helped him solve the given problem. He said that he never experienced difficulty while solving the given problem.

I looked at the sample of my teacher while solving to see if what I was doing was right. I then noticed that it was very similar to the samples our teacher gave so it wasn't difficult and my solving became much easier. (S5.3)

Similarly, S6.3, S7.2, and S7.3 mentioned that they compared their solution to the solution made by their teachers to see if they were doing it correctly. S6.3 added that the solution made by his teacher was not exactly the solution he made but he used it as a guide to help him arrive at his final answer. Also, S7.4 stated that the familiarity of the problem was really important for him. He explained that he never felt pressured while solving because he still remembered the process taught by them during the online session.

The same was true with S8.2, S9.1, and S10.4 who mentioned that familiarity of the problem helped them understand the interview questions. S9.1 said that the problem given to her was similar to the problem given by the teacher about ventral angle and intercepted arc and because of this, S10.4 stated that he never found difficulties in analyzing the problem.

2.2.2. Verifying Solutions

Verification solution was the second technique used by the students under monitoring regulation of cognition in terms of solving the given word problem. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as checking of work step-by-step, reflecting from time to time, and using a spare sheet of paper to draft a solution.

2.2.2.1. Checking Works Step by Step

Verifying solutions on monitoring regulation of cognition emphasized the skill of the students to check their work step-by-step as they went on with the problem. All the four students of T1 mentioned during the interviews that they checked their work step-by-step. S1.1 said that he checked his solution and answer many times and he felt comfortable with trying to think that he got his answer correctly.

Meanwhile, S1.3 stated that while she was solving, she stopped to check if she wrote the process coherently. Also, S1.4 reasoned out that he always made mistakes whenever he wrote fast and believed that one wrong written number could make his answer incorrect hence, it was better to check one's work frequently to provide an assurance. Lastly, S1.2 explained the importance of checking one's own work step by step as a monitoring procedure. She expounded that checking the given based on the problem and checking the graph based on the given would help her assure that her solution or calculation was correct.

S2.1 checked his solution to see what needed to be corrected and S2.3 revealed that she looked back on her solution to see whether she followed the correct procedure or not. S3.2 and S3.4 mentioned that they checked their work step by step to make sure that they were doing the right solution in connection to the given problem. Also, S3.2 revealed that he re-read his solution and to the question thoroughly because he would sometimes get confused if the given vertex should be written in the center of the circle or around its circumference.

S4.2 said that he frequently did check his work in depth for the reason that he was hesitant with his answer especially when the problem

required a long procedure. On the other hand, S5.2 revealed that he did checking repeatedly to see the connection of the problem to his graph or illustration and to inspect the listed given before he substituted them to the formula. The same is true with S5.1 who did checking regularly to make sure that he was doing the procedure correctly.

I also went back to it before and after I solved to see if first, I wrote the given points correctly; and second, I did the substitution correctly in the formula based on the given. (S5.1)

Both S6.1 and S6.2 of T6 revealed that they both reviewed their work from time to time to correct the mistakes they had made. S6.1 stated that she examined her work frequently to see the parts of her solution that she didn't understand. She added that sometimes forgot how to write her procedures in sequence and so mistakes were made especially in terms of basic operations.

Every time I solve, I would check my solution while doing so, especially during checking where I would look over that operation I am doing. It would be difficult if I make mistakes. (S6.1)

S7.2, S7.3, and S7.4 of T7 revealed that they often scanned their solution to determine if they committed mistakes while solving the problem. This would help them prevent committing the same errors and thus obtain valid answers. S8.4 and S9.4 stated that they sometimes felt hesitant with their answers. With this, they said during the interviews that they always went back to the problem and figured to check if they provided the correct solution and a certain answer. S10.1 stated that before he moved to the next step of the problem, he would try to make sure that he made steps which were congruent to his previously made decision and written solution because he admitted that sometimes he felt confused with his answer.

S11.2 and S11.4 of T11 together with S12.1 and S12.3 of T12 said that based on the given problem during their one-on-one interview, they felt confident with their answers because the problem was very familiar to them. The reason why they went back to their solution from time to time, although it was familiar to them, was because it was their usual habit instilled in them to look back on their solutions and answers.

2.2.2.2. Reflecting from Time to Time

This elaborated students' metacognitive strategy put emphasis on how learners reflect on their work from time to time. Learners usually did this to recall what they did to make sure that the solution was correct, to look back on the problem and analyze the procedure, to see the congruency of the answer to the given figure, and to determine if they were doing it right.

S4.1 explained his reason why he stopped from time to time. He said during the interview that he simply followed the steps to solve for the x in order to determine the specific measurement of the given circle, but at the same time, he stopped from time to time to see if he was doing the right process because he believed that sometimes due to his pace and careless in solving would lead him to commit unintentional mistakes.

S5.4 said that he forgot some details about the topic in the given problem that led him to pause from time to time to see if he was still doing the right process. The same happened with S7.1 who stated that he would pause while solving to go back to the problem and analyze the figure he made before he continued doing his solution.

S8.1 explained that since the given process questions were five, he thought that he was guided by the process to come up with the correct answer. He added that in every question, he always went back to the given to check if he wrote them correctly before moving to the next one.

On the other hand, S8.2 and S9.3 both said that they stopped from time to time to check their work. S9.3 explained that she went back to the figure she made to see if there was congruence between her solution and the labelled illustration of the circle.

I stopped frequently to see if I was doing it correctly. I kept looking back at the circle I drew to make sure of it and as well as to avoid repeating. (S9.3)

Furthermore, S11.3 said that he was so unsure of his procedure that he decided to stop in the middle of solving the problem to think and recall the technique taught to him in order to come up with a valid solution.

2.2.2.3. Using Scratch to Draft Solutions

This one was rarely stated by the students during the interview and only three learners mentioned this technique in solving the given word problem. S2.3 of T2 used to draft her solution on a separate sheet of paper to write all her ideas in and compiled them to generate the whole process.

Yes, so what I did first was to write down the solution on a sheet of paper. I also wrote all my ideas about the problem before I transferred them and organized everything on a clean sheet of paper. (S2.3)

S4.1 of T4 said that his reason why he used a scratch paper in solving the given word problem was for him to see the whole process first and review if something was missing or written incorrectly. He added that he really wanted to make his work neat as always.

Lastly, S7.4 used trial and error in solving the problem. She followed certain steps to answer the problem, stating that she must read

the problem carefully, identify the given, understand what is asked, and figure out the formula. However, she gave emphasis on trial and error before she finalized her solution on a separate piece of paper and to start where she thought would be easy for her.

But before everything else, get a piece of paper for the trial and error and start where you think is the easiest to answer. (S7.4)

In summary, students provided second thought upon solving the task. Learners think twice during the observation because they get confused on their process and think if they do the solution correctly. Hence, they were able to recognize errors from their work upon checking the steps from time to time. One thing, as well, that helped them to solve the problem was the familiarity which enabled them to reflect from the process from time to time. In addition, most of the learners were able to showcase checking of work from time to time and emphasized that familiarity of the problem had a great contribution in solving new problems. Lastly, few learners were able to write a draft of their solution in the problem.

A conscious monitoring is when learners ask themselves questions if they perform cognitive tasks correctly and observe how they do it. These may provide decisions that might work before, during, or after the learning process (du Toit & Kotze, 2009). Monitoring skills refer to the learners' skills and strategy utilized to process information more efficiently (e.g., organizing, elaborating, summarizing, and selective focusing). Efficient processing of information is evident when the learner gets involved in presenting the meaning of meaningful learning and discerns the manner of translating new information.

Mokos and Kafoussi (2013) affirmed that the efficiency of learners in monitoring owes to their ability to create focus and pay careful attention to important and relative information. The presentation of monitoring regulation of cognition in this study was central to the theme of meaningfulness in learning as it indicates relating previous and current understanding of the learner.

2.3. Learners' Evaluating Regulation

From the data on evaluating, reviewing the process and revising and drawing conclusion emerged as the major metacognitive strategies of teachers utilized by learners towards solving a problem. These strategies were elaborated by the implications of specific metacognitive strategies such as reviewing calculations and procedures, using strategies to check answers, thinking alternative ways after completing the task, revising the solution if not correct, and drawing conclusion.

2.3.1. Reviewing the Process

Reviewing the process was one among the techniques used by the students in terms of evaluation skills. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as to review calculations and procedures, to use strategies in checking answers, and to think of alternative ways after completing the task.

2.3.1.1. Reviewing Calculations and Procedures

Reviewing calculations and procedures indicate students' ability to check their work manually or through the use of a calculator and to determine if the process is correct. S1.1, S1.3, and S1.4 mentioned during the interview that they reviewed their calculations and procedures after completing the task. S1.1 stated that in all problem solving it was very important to check if the process of solution was performed well to prevent mistakes and see errors.

Problems had different ways to check their solutions, one may do it manually or opt to use a calculator. S1.4 stated that sometimes, due to time constraints in solving the problem, she would make mistakes in writing the sign of the integers or even writing wrong numbers. S1.3 explained that everything in the solution would be incorrect if there was something wrong even on one side of the given problem about distance formula. He added that it was how reviewing calculations and procedures work.

Apparently, S2.1 admitted that he did it manually and later used a calculator to confirm his answer. S2.4 did the same thing, saying that one wrong number could make the solution and answer invalid. Also, S2.2 looked back on her process to prove her solution and check her calculation.

Similarly, S3.1 said that it was very important for her to check and review her answer after her calculation. This gave her satisfaction with her solution and added that as long as she had enough time to do it, she would definitely check and review her solution for the sake of recognizing errors and mistakes. S3.2 revealed that the importance of reviewing procedures and calculation gave him assurance about his measurement in congruence to the given word problem. Also, S3.3 stated that there were times when she would overlook small details and mistakes due to cramming, hence, she gave importance on reviewing the procedure she made even for a quick moment. Finally, S3.4 said that reviewing calculations and procedures gave her a chance to correct her mistakes.

Contrarily, S5.1 mentioned that he reviewed his calculations due to hesitation in his answers although he got them correctly. He even requested an ample time for a quick review of his calculation and procedure. S5.2 double checked the given written on her paper because she admitted that she would often make mistakes in writing the sign of the given in the problem. S5.3 and S5.4 checked if they worked through the given correctly, substituted the given in congruence to the formula, and executed the operation accurately.

Yes, I reviewed everything after I solved for the answer. I also double checked how the given were computed, whether they were right, especially the signs since I would often make mistakes there. (S5.2)

Furthermore, S6.1, S6.2, and S6.3 of T6 also reviewed their calculations and procedures. S6.1 stated that she would sometimes be excited in answering the problem which would result in her making mistakes along the way, hence, for her, reviewing was very important to see an error or to check if she omitted something from the calculation or procedure. S6.2 agreed with her and mentioned that he would always look back on the process (as an attitude) whenever he needed to solve problems. And finally, S6.3 reviewed because he was so hesitant in his calculation.

Moreover, S7.1 and S7.2 said that they did review their work whenever they would solve a problem. In a similar way, S8.1 mentioned that after completing the task, he went back to the top of his solution to check the given, the illustration, the formula, and the process. S8.2 felt confident after checking his calculations and procedures and S8.4 reviewed his solution twice to check the operation he used during the calculation.

Similar to S8.4, S9.2, S11.2, S11.3, and S12.4 reviewed their calculations twice before finalizing their solutions. S10.1 and S10.2 used a calculator to check their calculation, saying that they sometimes proceed with the steps, committing some steps carelessly. Moreover, S10.3 looked back on the calculation because she was so hesitant with the formula she used during the interview.

2.3.1.2. Using Strategies to Check Answers

This elaborated metacognitive strategy presents different strategies to check if the answer is correct. Some concepts on how the learners checked their works were based on how it was taught by the teacher – through substitution method, backward method, or use of another formula which could be an alternative way to approach the problem about circle.

S1.1, S1.2, and S1.4 used Pythagorean Theorem to check their answers about the distance between two points. S1.2 said that he used Pythagorean Theorem by counting the points aligned with the diagonal line vertically and horizontally and resulted in both sides being 7 units. He obtained an answer which was similar to his answer in his solution thus proving that his answer was correct.

Similar to S1.2, S2.1, S2.2, and S2.3 also used Pythagorean Theorem to check if their answer was correct. Based on the statement of S2.2, she said that their teacher taught them how to check the problems regarding distance formula.

On the other hand, all the four students of T3 used a substitution method to check their answers about central angle and intercepted arc. According to S3.3, he used the root placing technique after he identified the value of x . From the equation $180 = x + 128 + x + 48$, he substituted the value of x and obtained a final answer of $180 = 180$. Since they were equal in value that indicated that their answer for x was correct.

It was for the checking process in which our answer was through root placing the value of x and it was what greatly helped us to make it easier or to know if our answer was right or wrong. (S3.3)

The same was true with S4.1, S4.2, and S4.4 who also used the substitution method to come up with the checking of their answers. Furthermore, S6.2, S6.3, and S6.4 who received the same problem as T3 students about central angle and intercepted arc used substitution method, as well, for checking their answer. S6.2 said that in order to ensure that his answer was correct, the answer to the checking process must be 180 degrees.

In a similar way, S7.1, S7.2, S7.3, S7.4, S8.1, S8.2, S9.1, S10.4, S11.2, S12.1, and S12.3 also used substitution method to check their answers. S8.2 mentioned that when units were counted from the graph, one needed to start from zero. S8.1 used the value of horizontal line which was 7 units and vertical line which was also 7 units to get the value of the hypotenuse of the right triangle hence, gaining an answer of $7\sqrt{2}$ which was similar to the result of her first procedure.

2.3.1.3. Thinking Alternative Ways after Completing the Task

Thinking alternative ways after completing a task was one among the elaborated strategies of evaluating regulation of cognition, which implies a skill to think of other options to approach a particular word problem after its completion. S1.1 thought on how to save time when solving distance between two points. He used the Pythagorean Theorem to think if he would get the same answer as the distance formula by counting the number of points vertically and horizontally adjacent to the horizontal line.

In similar ways as S1.1, S1.3, and S2.4 used the same alternative on how to find the length of the slant line or the hypotenuse of the right triangle.

The other approach I thought of to get {the answer} was to count the points which you can then use for the Pythagorean Theorem. I realized that the answers were correct since I counted the points, like from Gabriella's to Emilio's house. I counted them from zero then 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7. It takes 7 points to go to Emilio's house, which makes my answer 7 correct. (1.3)

2.3.2. Revising and Drawing Conclusion

Revising and drawing conclusions was another approach used by the students after solving the given task. This includes specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as to revise the solution if found incorrect and make a conclusion.

2.3.2.1. Revising the Solution if not Correct

During the interview, the interviewer noticed that there was something wrong with the calculation of S4.3. However, the interviewer did not mention where exactly the mistake made by S4.3 was and instead asked her to find the error. The student was able to look for it and changed it. Immediately, she mentioned that she just overlooked this part of the solution.

In a similar manner, S5.4 committed an error in terms of writing his formula. Instead of getting the difference between x_2 and x_1 as well as y_2 and y_1 , he used the addition operation. He was quick enough to notice the error he made while reading his answer during the interview.

Apparently, S6.3 wondered why his answer got more degrees than the half of the circle. Hence, he looked back on his procedure and discovered that instead of writing negative 176, he wrote positive 176, making him get a total of 256 degrees instead of 4 degrees.

I noticed that what I did first was wrong since I wrote down positive 176 instead of negative 176 and so it made me wonder why the answer, I arrived at was huge. It was much bigger than a half circle. Hahaha... and so I changed it. (S6.3)

Similar to S6.3, S7.2 admitted that he also made the same mistakes. Instead of writing $2x$ for the sum of x and x he wrote x^2 , but when he went back from the top, he was able to recognize his error and made a correction right away.

2.3.2.2. Drawing Conclusions

Drawing conclusions was another approach used by the learners in ending their solution in the given word problem. Usually, based on the answers of the learners during the interview, they would draw conclusions through the lead question of the given task.

S1.1, S1.2, S1.3, and S1.4 were able to draw conclusions after they arrived at their final answer and checking process. S1.2 said that the triangle formed in the problem was an isosceles right triangle and S1.3 stated that an isosceles triangle is a right triangle with two equal sides. S1.4 mentioned that the diameter was equal to 13 units as represented by points A and B. All these four students based their conclusion on the leading question of the given word problem.

Also, S2.2 mentioned during his interview that he drew a conclusion about the distance between the houses of Gabriella and Emilio, while S3.3 recognized that if the measurement of arc KJ and arc KG would be added, 180 degrees or a semi-circle would be formed.

Moreover, S5.2, S5.3, and S5.4 made their conclusion similar to what S1.4 did regarding the length of the diameter of the circle. Furthermore, S6.1, S6.2, S7.1, S9.1, S12.1, and S12.2, all of them received the problem on central angle and intercepted arc drew a conclusion that if the value of angle GLK was 130 degrees and value of angle KLJ was 50 degrees hence, the sum of the two angles was 180 degrees which represented the half of a circle which was also called a semi-circle.

Lastly, S8.3, S11.1, and S11.4 drew a conclusion that the distances of the houses forming a square with horizontal lines equivalent to 7 units away was similar to those houses with vertical lines while the diagonal line was $7\sqrt{2}$ units. The figure forming a right triangle with size equals 7 units each and the hypotenuse equals $7\sqrt{2}$ units.

In summary, students used more techniques in evaluating regulation of cognition in terms of revising and reviewing their solutions. In reviewing their calculations and procedures, they look back from top to bottom, from the given, formula, and even the process to see errors and to ensure that signs and operations were done correctly. They also used a substitution method and other strategies on how they would be able to check their final answer and draw a conclusion based on the lead question. However, only few learners were able to think of alternative ways after completing the task and revising the solution if incorrect since most of them were satisfied and confident with their processes.

Evaluation involves the analysis of performance and strategy effectiveness after a learner's learning episode. In this regard, Pulmones (2008) reiterated that learners' prolonged engagement in constructivist designed classes has demonstrated cognitive regulation behaviors, including evaluation behaviors. Notes of ambiguities, discrepancies, faults, observations, and ways to fix their errors are made by learners. If more knowledge is collected or obtained through feedback from evaluation, preliminary insights can be correlated with changes in those insights that evaluation should facilitate mathematics learning (Costa, 1984; Blakey & Spence, 1990; NCTM, 2000).

Metacognitive Strategies of Teachers Used by Learners

From the metacognitive strategies of teachers used by learners that emerged from their solutions during the interviews, there were eleven (11) learning strategies that define how learners learn mathematical knowledge and skills in solving word problems from the instruction and assessment of teachers (see figure 1).

There are two metacognitive components (knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition) with three types for each metacognitive component that have investigated. For knowledge of cognition, there are three types of metacognition- declarative, procedural, and conditional while three types under teachers' regulation of cognition that include planning, monitoring, and evaluating.

For declarative, there are two metacognitive strategies which are activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information while substituting, representing, and organizing solutions for procedural and questioning the problem and

own practices with generating solutions for conditional.

For planning, there are two metacognitive strategies which are breaking down, illustrating, and labelling and thinking about information, formulas, and steps while making sense on owns work and verifying solutions for monitoring and reviewing the process and revising and drawing conclusions strategies for evaluating.

Activating Concepts on the Problem	Substituting, Representing, and Organizing Solutions	Questioning the Problem and Own Practices Generating Solutions	Breaking Down, Illustrating, and Labelling	Making Sense on Owns Work Verifying Solutions	Reviewing the Process Revising and Drawing Conclusions
Identifying and Determining concepts and Information			Thinking about Information, Formulas, and Steps		
Declarative	Procedural	Conditional	Planning	Monitoring	Evaluating
Knowledge of Cognition			↔	Regulation of Cognition	

Figure 1. Model of Metacognition in Mathematics Learning

As to the student’s knowledge of cognition, their declarative knowledge manifests activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information techniques which include specific and elaborated learners’ metacognitive strategies such as read and recall, translate, identify and determine concepts and information, and understand the leading question.

Activating concepts on the problem is the process of rehearsing information to recall a list of items, its meaning and use to be able to translate the content of the problem (Santrock, 2011). Activating concepts was one of the cognitive strategies used by the students in solving the given word problem during the interview.

This provides attribution among learners to read and recall the lesson intended for the topic and translate the concepts in the problem based on the level of their understanding. These attributions among learners offer an ability to understand and think of ways on how to approach the problem (Santrock, 2011).

The learners in this study provided information regarding ways of developing knowledge metacognitively. They expressed the benefit of reading and recalling. Beyond argument, indeed, rereading has both superficial and in-depth learning implications. While learners’ working memory appears to be within reach, repeated reading provides learning stored in the long-term memory. Moreover, they identified and discovered that there are more strategic approaches to learning. The attempt to repeated reading leads to deep learning and later, learners’ bank onto their long-term memory for retrieval, eventually the process of retrieving connects to one’s superior cognition called executive function (Willis, 2007). The process of activating concepts via repeated reading allows learners easy access to stored information from the long-term memory (Aisami, 2015).

In addition, identifying and determining concepts and information and understanding the lead questions were used to link older information to new concepts. In fact, identifying and determining concepts and information is an effective memory strategy across a variety of learning tasks that add distinctiveness to the new information (Woolfolk, 2013).

Furthermore, student’s procedural knowledge includes substituting, representing, and organizing process, which include specific strategies that elaborate concepts such as substitution process, use of representation while solving, and organizing solutions coherently and logically.

Substituting, representing, and organizing process is the execution of plan, strategy, model, idea, decision, or method and the realization of an application of the subject. This promotes better clarity of thoughts that improves one’s own realization and understanding about the lesson.

It facilitates the execution of plans by breaking down the process into smaller steps using the limited resources provided in the problem, using substitution and representations while solving, and organizing solutions coherently and logically (William, 2010). These are the elaborated metacognitive strategies used by learners in solving word problems that show attribution to the process used by the learners in solving word problems.

Moreover, a student's conditional knowledge elaborated from the questioning the problem and own practices and generating solutions, which include specific learners’ strategies that elaborate concepts such as questioning the problem, consistent practice to develop familiarity, identifying solutions’ appropriateness, and exploring possibilities.

Questioning the problem and own practices play a vital role in a meaningful and motivating learning, which assists learners’

comprehension about the problem. Students' ability to generate questions improves their critical and creative thinking skills to assigned tasks. This may be used with the help of their teachers or they may generate questions on their own. In fact, generating questions can reinforce the connection between learning and assessment (Papinczak et al., 2012).

Generating questions was one of the techniques used by the students to identify what formula was suited to the given problem, what went wrong and what went right, and when and why to use such strategies, techniques, or approach in solving the problem. This theme provides attribution among learners to question the problem, be familiar with it through consistent practice, and think of ways on how to approach the given task.

In addition, generating solution is the process of discovering new ways to approach the problem to bridge the current state of the procedures (Yu, 2012). This process is the ability of the learner to devise his own strategy to elevate the level of approach for a particular learning process, which constantly estimates and calibrates the capability to do the task and later perform it. Generating solutions offers attribution to explore alternative ways and identify appropriate solutions to the given word problem.

As to students' regulation of cognition, the planning regulation manifests breaking down, illustrating, and labelling and thinking about the information, formula, and steps which include specific learners' strategies as to writing down the information in the problem, determining the required formula, thinking about the steps before solving, breaking down the problem, drawing illustration, and putting labels.

Breaking down, illustrating, and labelling concepts help learners to understand the problem, visualize it, see the missing parts of the problem, decide what formula is needed, figure out the context of the task, and see the bigger picture of the problem (Montague, 2015). While, thinking about the information, formulas, and steps give the learners a chance to select the operation intended or necessary for a given problem and at the same time decide regarding the best way on how to set up the given word problem (Montague, 2015). In this section, the attribution to write down the needed information, determine the required formula, and think about all the necessary steps to solve the given task are highlighted.

In a similar manner, student's monitoring regulation presents making sense on owns work and verifying solutions, which include specific learners' strategies that elaborate concepts such as providing a second thoughts, recognizing errors, familiarity on the problem, checking works step by step, reflecting from time to time, and using scratch to draft solutions.

Making sense of one's own work and verifying solutions are the essence of solving problem that requires understanding and decision about the situation to find and to choose suitable procedure from the mistakes or errors made in the problem. It is a second-thought experience that begins in our intention to comprehend particular interpretation in a problem-situation. Consciously, one starts looking for the components or parts of the procedures and connect them as emerging errors are recognized while doing the process. The prior knowledge to interpret, decode, and provide meaning as we search, decide, interpret, identify, question, and choose become an avenue to be familiar with the problem (Kuhlthau, 1991). Sense making involves attribution to second thoughts, recognizing errors and problem's familiarity, which help learners to better understand the solving process, judge their thinking, see errors before writing the final answer, and be oriented whenever they encounter similar problems.

Solution verification, on the other hand, addresses the problem situation by checking and reflecting from the work from time to time and by questioning whether the materials are sufficiently accurate for its intended use. It is also a process of estimating the numerical errors in the problem (Kuhlthau, 1991). Verification was the second technique used by the students under monitoring regulation of cognition in terms of solving the given word problem that offers attribution to check work step by step, reflect from time to time, and use scratch to draft a solution.

Finally, student's evaluating regulation was elaborated from the utilization of metacognitive strategies such as reviewing and revising which include specific utilization of strategies that elaborate concepts to review calculations and procedures, use strategies to check answers, draw conclusions, think of alternative ways after completing a task, and revising solutions if not correct.

Reviewing, in the context of problem solving, means to reconsider, to look again, to rectify an error made, or to re-examine calculations and procedures and think different strategies to check the answer before writing the conclusion while revising is an act of making changes, adjustments, or improvements from the process one made during the calculation, which allows learners to correct some errors they made and think for an alternative solution after solving a problem (Polya, 1971).

The rounded arrow in the figure above shows the metacognitive learning acquired by select learners from the instruction and assessment of the teacher-participants of the study and these are parallel processes which implies that these metacognitive strategies were used by the learner-participants based on the condition and requirements needed in the given word problems during the interview.

Metacognitive learning can help learners to create meaningful experiences. These meaningful experiences depend on the teachers who are considered the facilitator of learning. In the study of Killen (2000), as cited by du Toit and Kotze (2009), problem solving is a great avenue for learners to enhance their metacognition, generally, a self-aware learner is a good problem solver. Problem solving skills enhance when the existing knowledge is applied to the situation and it requires reflection to one's own thinking, which develops metacognitive skills. As the hallmarks of mathematics education, which aims to develop learners as good problem solvers, problem solving becomes the greatest goal of mathematics educators to develop and enhance learners' metacognitive thinking (NCTM, 2000).

Conclusions

When using metacognition to word problem solving in mathematics, the two metacognitive components serve as an explicit anchor for the strategies used in problem solving. Specific metacognitive strategies, such as activating concepts on the problem and identifying and determining concepts and information techniques, such as specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts like reading and recalling, translating, identifying mathematical concepts, determining the needed information, and understanding the leading question, were used by the students to demonstrate their declarative knowledge of cognition in mathematics learning.

Specific metacognitive strategies, such as substituting, representing, and organizing process—which involve the specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to the substitution process, using representation while solving, and organizing solution logically and coherently—were used by students' procedural knowledge in mathematics learning. The implementation of an application of the subject and the execution of a plan, strategy, model, idea, decision, or procedure are the substituting, representing, and organizing processes. In order to question the problem and their own practices—which include specific implication of strategies that elaborate concepts to question the problem, consistent practice to develop familiarity, solution appropriateness, exploring possible solutions, and thinking of ways to approach the problem—students' conditional knowledge in mathematics learning made use of particular metacognitive strategies.

Students' use of specific metacognitive strategies, such as breaking down, illustrating, and labeling, as well as thinking about the information, formula, and steps, were utilized in their regulation of cognition during mathematics learning. These strategies included the specific application of strategies that elaborate concepts to write down the problem's information, determine the necessary formula, consider the steps before solving it, break down the problem, draw an illustration of it, and label it.

In order to monitor their progress in learning mathematics, students used a variety of metacognitive strategies, including making sense of their own work and verifying solutions. These included applying strategies that elaborate concepts to give ideas second thoughts both during and after solving problems, identifying errors in the solution, being familiar with the problem, going over work step-by-step, reflecting occasionally, and drafting solutions using scratch. Specific metacognitive strategies were used by students to evaluate their learning of mathematics. These strategies included reviewing and revising, which involves applying specific implications of strategies that elaborate concepts to review calculations and procedures, using strategies to check answers, draw conclusions, and consider alternative solutions after finishing a task.

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the extension of metacognition to learning gives new perspectives in categorizing specific and elaborated metacognitive strategies that mathematics teachers use and students' learning strategies acquire from mathematical discussion. Linking these specific metacognitive strategies through the lens of learning will promote more productive and meaningful classroom discussion.

Only the six categories of metacognition in learning are covered in this study. Therefore, in order to further enhance the model, it is advised that future researchers take into account the other two categories of metacognitive learning that are still in existence, namely information management techniques and debugging methods. Similarly, researchers may examine methods of teaching training, especially examining the six types of metacognition with a large sample of pre-service education programs.

In order to improve students' metacognition and promote this way of thinking, pre-service mathematics teachers can use this study's model to learn about various metacognitive strategies. They can also gain a thorough understanding of metacognition and the connections between various representations and concepts.

The results of this study shed light on learning strategies used in classrooms. In order to give teachers knowledge on how to assist students in understanding their problem-solving process and investigating internal and external linkages in mathematics, this study may be applied to graduate teacher education programs and in-service training.

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